

Action Sheet

Issue	Responsability	Resources and Actions	Estimated Cost (€)	Time Frame
#1 Clear and consistent menu icons <i>(Learnability)</i>	Development	Tools: – Material Icons or FontAwesome Actions: 1. Audit and map current icons in the Figma prototype. 2. Replace all ambiguous icons and add concise tooltips using microcopy. 3. Deploy updated assets (CSS/HTML) and validate via a quick usability test with five participants.	199 €	Short-term (1–2 m)
#2 Onboarding and contextual guidance <i>(Learnability)</i>	Content & Development	Tools: – Figma; DaVinci Resolve / CapCut / Camtasia Actions: 1. Produce five brief text-based “quick tips” and two micro-videos (≤ 15 s each) explaining core features. 2. Design a responsive welcome modal for mobile. 3. Trigger the modal on first visit (via local Storage/cookie) and measure its click-through rate.	0 € <i>(minimum-cost scenario)</i> ¹	Short-term (1–2 m)
#3 Basic performance optimizations (LCP < 2 s) and resilience under load <i>(Efficiency / Errors)</i>	Development	Tools: – Lighthouse CI, WebP conversion tool, Lazy-Load JS, Locust (load testing) Actions: 1. Run a Lighthouse audit to identify assets > 100 KB. 2. Convert critical images to WebP and implement lazy-loading. 3. Conduct load tests simulating 1 000 concurrent users; identify failure points. 4. Add retry logic and a circuit breaker to the front-end.	0 €	Medium-term (3–6 m)
#4 Direct navigation to “My Teams” (reducing multi-tap) <i>(Efficiency / Memorability)</i>	Development	Tools: – Figma, React Navigation Actions: 1. Map the existing navigation flow and identify the optimal entry point. 2. Add a persistent “My Teams” shortcut in the bottom menu or implement a swipe gesture. 3. Test on real devices (TestFlight/Play Console) to reduce taps from four to one.	0 €	Short-term (1–2 m)
#5 Subscription model, ad-adjustment & feedback <i>(Satisfaction)</i>	Commercial Relations & Development	Tools: – Stripe / Paypal / Mbyway, Google Ad Manager; Hotjar Surveys; PlanOut (A/B testing) Actions: 1. Configure “Ad-free” plan (€1.99/mo) and cap free-tier ad density to 1 banner/3 screens. 2. Update Google Ad Manager rules to enforce ad caps and serve paid-plan with no ads. 3. Integrate in-app NPS/CSAT widget (Hotjar Surveys) at key points and conduct A/B tests (PlanOut) on ad formats and feedback prompts to optimize adherence and satisfaction.	0 € <i>(minimum-cost scenario)</i> ²	Medium-term (3–6 m)
#6 Error monitoring, inline messages & “Undo” <i>(Errors)</i>	Helpdesk & Development	Tools: – Sentry, Grafana; Yup/Formik; React-Toastify Actions: 1. Integrate Sentry into both front-end and back-end to capture silent failures. 2. Configure alerts in Grafana (email/Slack) for error rates exceeding 1% of requests. 3. Validating forms with Yup/Formik, displaying error messages inline and reporting faults to Sentry. 4. Add “undo” toasts (React-Toastify) to destructive actions. 5. Use feature-flags: gradual rollout, monitor errors in real time and automatic rollback if rate >0.5 % in 10 min.	288 €	Long-term (6–12 m)

Total Incremental Tool Cost: € 487 per year

Overall Time Frame: 12 months

¹ As far as the free version of Figma and DaVinci Resolve or Cap Cut (free version) is concerned.

² Without Hotjar Business subscription

A. Gantt Chart

(12-month scenario)

Gantt view in table form, showing each issue’s execution window across the 12-month horizon:

ISSUE	QUARTER 1				QUARTER 2				QUARTER 3			
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
1. Clear and consistent menu icons	█	█										
2. Onboarding and contextual guidance		█	█									
3. Basic performance optimizations & resilience under load					█	█	█	█				
4. Direct navigation to “My Teams” (reduce multi-tap)		█	█	█								
5. Subscription model & ad-adjustment						█	█	█	█			
6. Error monitoring & feedback during peak traffic							█	█	█	█	█	█

B. Estimated costs³

Issue 1

- [FontAwesome Pro](#) (icon set) –199 € /yr⁴
- [Material Icons](#) – free

Issue 2

- Figma (Free version)
- Video-creation:
 - DaVinci Resolve – Free
 - CapCut
 - Free version
 - Pro – 149,99 € / year
 - Camtasia
 - Camtasia Essentials – US\$179.88 / year ≈ 165.49 € / year
 - Camtasia Create – US\$249.00 / year ≈ 229.08 € / year
 - Camtasia Pro – US\$599.00 / year ≈ 551.08 € / year
- Small JS modal library (e.g. [Micromodal](#)) – free

Issue 3

- [Lighthouse CI](#) – free (open source)
- [WebP converter](#) (cwebp) – free
- [Locust](#) (load testing) – free

Issue 4

- [Figma](#) (flow mapping) – free version
- [React Navigation](#) – free

Issue 5

- [Stripe](#): free
 - 1.5 % + €0.25 per transaction
- [PayPal](#): free
 - Payment financed by card without a PayPal account: 1.20 % + flat fee
 - QR code transactions - ≥ € 10.01 0.90 % + flat fee
 - QR code transactions - ≤ € 10.00 1.40 % + flat fee
 - All other commercial transactions 2.90 % + flat fee
- [MB Way](#): free
- [Google Ad Manager](#) – free
- [Hotjar](#) – Free
 - Hotjar Business – 80 € /mo × 12 mo = 960 € /yr.

Issue 6

- [Sentry Team](#) (error tracking)
 - \$26 / monthly per user; billed annually → ≈ 288 € / yr
- [Grafana Cloud](#) (dashboards) – free tier up to 10k series
- [Yup + Formik](#) – Free
- [React-Toastify](#) – Free

³ All labour is covered by existing salaried staff; the costs reflect only new tool licenses or subscriptions.

⁴ Font Awsome Pro – For the creation of custom iconography

C. Consideration of Personnel-Related Costs

Although the main cost table presented in this study does not include personnel costs, it is important to acknowledge that human resources represent a significant portion of any digital transformation effort. Since the implementation would rely primarily on internal staff from ZeroZero, and detailed information about internal salaries or time allocation per task was not available, these costs were not integrated into the central estimate.

Nevertheless, an indicative salary table was compiled and is provided. This table includes average gross and net salaries, as well as estimated hourly rates for relevant job roles based on national statistics, market platforms, and public funding references (e.g., Portugal 2020/2030). It can serve as a useful starting point for internal cost estimations or resource planning.

Job Role	Average Gross Salary (monthly)	Estimated Net Salary (monthly)	Hourly Rate (Portugal 2020/2030 ref.)
National Minimum Wage (2025)	870 €	~774 € (tax-exempt)	~5 €/h
Software Developer	~1,673 €	~1,300 €	~14 €/h
Frontend Developer	~2,917 €	~1,900 €	~20 €/h
Backend Developer	~3,840 € (~53,657 €/year)	~2,400 €	~23 €/h (ranges 17–30 €/h)
UX Writer	~4,357 € (~52,284 €/year)	~2,800 €	~25 €/h
Content Strategist	~3,690 € (Lisbon: ~44,279 €/year)	~2,400 €	~21 €/h (Lisbon avg.)
Account Manager	~1,670 €	~1,250 €	~14 €/h
Customer Success Manager	~3,133 € (~37,597 €/year)	~2,050 €	~18 €/h
Sales Executive	~1,292 € (excl. commissions)	~1,000 €	~10–12 €/h
IT Support Specialist	~1,282 €	~970 €	~17 €/h
Technical Support (Helpdesk)	~1,140 €	~900 €	~15 €/h (est.)

C.1 References

PLUXEE. *Minimum Wage in Portugal: 2025 Updates* [online]. Available at: <https://www.pluxee.pt/blog/salario-minimo-em-portugal-atualizacoes-2025/>. [Accessed 24 July 2025].

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